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REQUIREMENTS MANAGEMENT FROM AN INTERDISCIPLINARY POINT OF VIEW

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ABSTRACT

An integrated modeling approach is presented to consider requirements in an interdisciplinary development project. Targets and requirements on system level are consistently decomposed into requirements for different disciplines using extended SysML and UML notation. Although, specific development, testing, and verification techniques in the different disciplines are used, the consistent fulfillment of requirements is monitored and possible goal conflicts are identified as soon as in the early phases. The approach is shown for the development of parallel robotic systems from mechanical and software related viewpoints that are integrated on system level.

Keywords: requirements management, interdisciplinary development, SysML/UML.

INTRODUCTION

In history of design research the awareness of ones targets has always been a main success factor for the development of good products. Still the management of requirements plays an important role and is subject to many research projects (Schenkl, Ponn & Lindemann, 2011), (Chahadi & Birkhofer, 2008), (Gausemeier, Frank, Donoth & Kahl, 2008), (Laplante, 2009). However, development processes and requirements management went different ways in different disciplines. In present days many products (e.g. robotic systems) are developed interdisciplinary and development processes as well as requirements management have to synchronize. The first step to bring the disciplines together is to understand their differences and similarities. The

authors analyzed 60 development processes and special requirements management approaches from mechanical engineering (e.g. Kesselring (1954)), electronics (e.g. (Wolf, 1994)), systems engineering (e.g. Daenzer & Huber, 2002), and software (e.g. (Robertson & Robertson, 2008)). Modules were described that appear in almost every development process, although names and description are often slightly different. In some approaches these modules are mentioned explicitly, defined as a particular step of the process, and supported by methods and software tools. In others approaches they are just mentioned but not defined or supported. Some approaches do not mention them at all, even if they contain essential steps to development success. The analysis led to the hypothesis that a consistent modeling of requirements with SysML/UML is a key to interdisciplinary product development. The analyzed approaches are summarized in Table 1 and the complete reference details can be found in (Stechert, 2010).

This contribution briefly shows modeling techniques for an interdisciplinary requirements management that were developed and used in the collaborative research project "Robotic Systems for Handling and Assembly" (SFB 562) (e.g. Stechert & Franke, 2009). Parallel robots are made up out of closed kinematic chains, i.e. a minimum of two kinematic chains is connected in parallel starting from the base frame and ending at the working platform. In such architecture drives can be mounted at or near to the base frame. This results in small moved mass and thus the potential for high dynamic movements. Additionally, a high stiffness can be provided. However, complexity of the system is higher and control is more difficult, e.g. because of singularities

REQUIREMENTS MANAGEMENT

At first, requirements on system level were identified and their relations to overall project targets, such as “provide high dynamic of the robotic system”, were established (Stechert, Franke & Vietor 2010) and documented in a SysML model (OMG, 2010). This target is satisfied by requirements of the mechanical subsystem and of the software subsystem. Thus, the target can just be reached if requirements from both disciplines are satisfied at the same time. Moreover, an overachievement in one discipline would not necessarily lead to a better product, but costs will be higher. For instance, if the kinematic structure moves very fast, but has to wait for new input data because of slow data transfer or vice versa the robotic system will not reach the target. Modeling methodology and analysis tools were developed to support early identification of (interdisciplinary) goal-conflicts (Stechert, Franke & Vietor 2010).

Model based development is widely appreciated in the embedded systems domain to cope with the complexity. As a generic and standardized approach UML has established as one of the most important notations for modeling software and with the extension SysML the scope was expanded to system modeling. The MARTE profile (UML Profile for Modeling and Analysis of Real-Time and Embedded systems) (OMG, 2009) makes domain specific ideas relevant for real-time and embedded systems design available in a unified modeling framework. Using the MARTE Profile enables the possibility to capture real-time/scheduling parameters and requirements in a UML design model.

A UML (Unified Modeling Language) Profile provides a generic extension mechanism to adapt the UML to a particular domain (e.g. aerospace, healthcare, ...) or platform (.NET, J2EE, ...). These extension mechanisms allow a refinement of the standard semantics. UML Profiles consist of stereotypes and tagged values that are applied to specific model elements (Classes, Operations, ...). Figure 3 gives an example of UML MARTE Profile elements added to a UML class. In this example, two stereotypes are used (`<<schedulableResource>>`, `<<saExecStep>>`) to define, that the method `store()` represents a task. Additionally, to parameterize the task, tagged values (characterized as a note block) are used to define the deadline, the priority, the execution time, etc.

Figure 3. An example of an application of the UML MARTE Profile.

Figure 2 shows a part of a requirement diagram. This diagram is built in extended SysML notation. It visualizes the hierarchic goal system and related objects such as use cases and components. Relations between objects can have character such as *refine*, *satisfy*, *allocate*, or *trace*. Whereas traces between requirements (and components) can be formalized by mathematic/ physic equations in form of *constraints*. If a relation cannot be described in formulas (e.g. because in concept phase necessary information is too few) the relation can be marked qualitatively

Figure 2. This part of a requirement diagram in extended SysML notation shows the hierarchic goal system and related use cases, components, and relations (e.g. constraints) between the objects.

(e.g. with use of expert experience or empirical data). In Figure 2 a *trace* was set between CPU power and work cycle. If conventional techniques are used these two requirements are conflicting, i.e. a CPU with high work cycle is normally of high power, thus energy consuming, thus not intended. This conflict was found within one knowledge discipline: software. Other conflicts are found in the knowledge discipline mechanics. Now, is it possible to find conflicts between “knowledge islands”? Yes, it is! Firstly, the main traces between requirements within the disciplines are modeled. Secondly, some obvious interdisciplinary traces between requirements are found and modeled. Then, a tool is able to identify additional conflicts on the basis of the known conflicts (Stechert, 2010). However, intelligent developers have to decide whether the conflict must be considered.

In the example two overall system goals are to provide a short cycle time and to provide a sustainable product. To use these statements for the development of the robotic system they are described more related to the robot as targets: “Develop a high dynamic robotic system” and “Develop a robotic system with little energy consumption”. The two targets are described more precisely as requirements. For instance, we can speak of a high dynamic robotic system if an acceleration of 100 m/s^2 or a maximum speed of 10 m/s is reached at the working platform. This can be satisfied by selecting powerful drives. On the other hand, a robotic system is said to be high dynamic if operations fit into a certain work cycle. This requirement is allocated to a CPU (component of the system).

Now looking at the energy consumption requirements regarding CPU and drive power were formulated. Thus, to develop a sustainable robot energy efficient drives are needed as well as energy efficient CPUs. In addition, trajectories have to be optimized regarding energy efficiency and efficiency factor of drives and kinematic structure (not shown in the diagram). Scheduling of the software tasks is also important.

However, already on systems level it is apparent that there is a conflict between low energy consumption and high dynamic. Moreover, the conflict is not only related to one discipline but must be considered

from a mechanical and software viewpoint at the same time.

In order to verify that a requirement is fulfilled, it is necessary to use different verification tools. For example, scheduling analysis can be made with SymTA/S (Henia, Hamann, Jersak, Racu, Richter & Ernst, 2005) or Times (Fersman & Yi, 2004). A verification if the robot structure is able to bear the load is made with multi body analysis (to simulate the load according to dynamics) and finite element analysis (to simulate stress and strain in the components).

Mechanical viewpoint

In the mechanical subsystem requirements related to dynamic are decomposed into subrequirements concerning drives and kinematic structure, as well as gripper and joints. Drives should provide a high acceleration and high rotational speed (see Figure 2). However, the transmission ratio of the kinematic structure (e.g. length of rods) together with payload must also be considered to define the “right” drive specifications: High payload and big workspace (i.e. long rods) leads to high demanded drive torque. On the other side, powerful drives are often energy consuming. If a goal “sustainability” is important (e.g. as marketing factor) a goal conflict becomes apparent. Now the system view shows that not only the drives but also the CPU contributes notably to the systems whole energy consumption. This influence is notable if the control tasks are distributed between several control computers. Thus, an optimization in software could save that amount of energy that is needed for more powerful drives.

Another goal conflict appears, if the requirements set of a joint is observed. The aforementioned system targets “high dynamic” and “low energy consumption” are transformed into a subsystem requirement “low friction”. A system target “high accuracy” is transformed into a subsystem requirement “high stiffness”. However, a conventional passive joint cannot be stiff and provide low friction at the same time. Adaptronic joints were developed that can be both, by means of a separation in time: a piezo actuator makes the joint stiff during assembly operations (small clearance in the bearings) and provides low friction

Figure 4. Abstracted flow chart of a pick-and-place cycle according to mechanic subsystems gripper, kinematic structure, and joints.

during high speed movements (bigger clearance in the bearings) (Pavlovic, Otremba, Inkermann, Franke & Vietor, 2010).

It was explained that adaptronic joints influence functional system requirements, according to accuracy, energy consumption, and dynamics. They also influence the dynamic of the whole system by terms of time requirements. In Figure 4 an abstracted flow chart of a pick-and-place cycle is shown. From the mechanical viewpoint three main components are involved: gripper, kinematic structure, and adaptronic joints. The operation starts with a fast movement to the pick position. When the pick position is reached a slower movement is necessary for precise positioning of the gripper. At the same time the joint stiffness should be high, so that the adaptronic joints are shifted into “stiff mode”. After positioning, the gripper closes to grasp the object. Then friction in the joints is reduced and a fast movement to place position starts. Just before the place position is reached joint friction is increased. This effects the deceleration in two ways: firstly, each joint works as an additional break to reduce the braking time. Secondly, the higher friction can be used to improve decay of oscillations. Thus, the structure does not need to wait very long to start the fine positioning of the gripper. After positioning, the gripper opens and the cycle is finished.

Software viewpoint

The requirement of processing and delivering input data for the kinematic structure in time is directly related to the task scheduling (e.g. deadlines of tasks). The demonstrators, which have been

developed in the collaborative research center (SFB 562) move very fast (up to 10 m/s) and achieve high accelerations (up to 100 m/s²). The high velocities induced several hard real-time constraints on the software architecture that has been designed to control the robots. PROSA-X (Parallel Robots Software Architecture - eXtended) is a generic architecture, which is used to control several different robots. PROSA-X offers the possibility to use multiple control PCs to distribute its algorithmic load (Steiner, Goltz & Maass, 2009). A specifically tailored middleware (MiRPA-X) and a bus protocol that operates on top of a FireWire bus (IAP) realize communication satisfying the hard real-time constraints (Kohn, Varchmin, Steiner & Goltz, 2004). The architecture is based on a layered design with multiple real-time layers within the operating system to realize e.g. a deterministic execution order for critical tasks (Maass, Kohn & Hesselbach, 2006). Figure 5 depicts an abstraction of the work cycle of the robotic control system. It consists of a control computer (“Control PC1”), which performs various computing tasks. The control computer is connected via a FireWire (IEEE 1394) data bus with a number of other processors (“DSP 1-7”, exemplarily represented by “DSA_1” in Figure 5). The DSPs supervise and control the machine. There is no deadline on a specific task, but there are deadlines on task chains/workflows (collections of depended tasks that are executed after another). The first task chain (starting point marked with 1) receives the instantaneous values and calculates the new setpoint values (Tasks: IAP_D, HWM, DC, SMC). The deadline for this is after 250 microseconds. The second task chain (starting point marked with 2)

Figure 5. Abstracted flow chart of the software work cycle.

contains the sending of the setpoint values to the DSPs and their processing (Tasks: IAP_M, MDT, IAP_N1, ..., IAP_N7, DDT1, ..., DDT7). This must be finished within 750 microseconds. Finally, the third chain (starting point marked with 3) comprises the control of the sensor and motion modules (Tasks: CC, CON, FOR, CFF, POS, VEL, SEN, SAP) and has to be completed within 1945 microseconds. This calculation is very complex and has to be done within a cycle. If these hard deadlines are missed, this could cause damage to the robot and its environment. To avoid such problems, a capturing and observation of these timing and scheduling requirements is necessary.

VERIFICATION

The first step of requirements management is to gather all relevant requirements. The next step is to process the often huge amount of requirements to delete redundancies, find conflicts, and harmonize requirements spreads. Then adjusted requirements sets are provided to the developers as a basis for their development. However, the fulfillment of the requirements must be tested during development, e.g. to decide which concept should be followed,

and at the end of the project to verify that the developed product fulfills the intended targets and requirements.

With an object oriented model test results can be traced back to assess the satisfaction of requirements. For each requirement a test criteria can be formulated and test cases can be defined, how to test and when to test during development. For instance, if allowed drive forces exceed can be tested in multi body simulation when a representative trajectory was defined. To verify whether an adaptive joint is able to increase the stiffness of the robot bench tests are needed: at first component tests on a joint test bench. Later integration tests with a robotic structure. For more information about object-oriented requirements and test models refer to (Stechert & Vietor, 2011). Although the use of adaptronic joints is able to reduce cycle times it brings one mayor disadvantage: adaptronic joints are more expensive than basic passive joints. Additionally, control equipment and software is necessary. Thence, the related conflict is not bipolar but (at least) tripolar. High dynamic, good accuracy, and low costs are difficult to reach at the same time. However, it is not possible to judge this conflict from a mere mechanical viewpoint. For

Figure 6. UML Scheduling Analysis View including the software tasks and the hardware tasks.

a cost estimation electronic parts must be considered, too. A statement about reachable accuracy can just be made together with control experts. An assessment of dynamic is just possible together with the scheduling of the whole system. To keep track of these timing requirements, they are captured in a model, the UML Scheduling Analysis View (Hagner & Huhn, 2008), including all scheduling/timing relevant parameters. The UML Scheduling Analysis View was designed regarding the information required by a number of scheduling analysis tools. Therefore, it concentrates on and highlights timing and scheduling aspects. Unlike usual design models, it contains all necessary information for an analysis (priorities, scheduling algorithms, task execution times, estimated by experts, measured, or calculated by tools like aiT (Ferdinand, Heckmann, Langenbach, Martin, Schmidt, Theiling, Thesing & Wilhelm, 2001), etc.). These parameters are added using the UML Profile MARTE (OMG, 2009).

The UML Scheduling Analysis View consists of class and object diagrams to describe the structure of the system (hardware resources, (software) tasks, and the mapping between these elements) and activity diagrams to describe the dependencies of the tasks (e.g. “Task A” has to be finished before “Task B” is activated), and to specify task chains.

Figure 6 depicts the software architecture of the robotic control system and the mechanical tasks and resources as a UML Scheduling Analysis View. The resources are depicted using the stereotypes `<<SaExecHost>>` (for a CPU or a mechanical resource)

or the `<<SaCommHost>>` (for a communication bus). The allocation of tasks on resources is specified using associations (marked with the `<<allocated>>` stereotype) between the classes that contain tasks (marked with the `<<schedulableResource>>` stereotype) and the resources. Additionally, there is an activity diagram for each task chain described in Section Requirements Management - Software Viewpoint. One example of a software task chain is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Activity diagram of one part of the software flow.

As mentioned, the UML Scheduling Analysis View depicted in Figure 6 includes the mechanical part (Requirements Management - Mechanical Viewpoint). Resources like the “gripper”, the “kinematic structure”, and the “adaptronic joints” are represented as execution hosts, those are able to execute tasks (in this case mechanical tasks e.g. “move to pick position” or “close gripper”). The mechanical tasks are represented as software tasks using the `<<allocated>>` and the `<<saExecStep>>`

stereotypes. Additionally, the dependencies of the mechanical tasks are described in activity diagrams. The example, presented in Section Requirements Management - Mechanical Viewpoint is depicted in Figure 8. It defines in which order the mechanical tasks have to be executed.

The parameterization of the mechanical part of the UML Scheduling Analysis View is done using mathematical calculation or measurement. The resources are using “First come, First serve” as a scheduling algorithm for their tasks. If faster resources are used (e.g. using a process with an adaptive joint), for the analysis it is only necessary to change the speed factor of the resource in the UML Scheduling Analysis View to define the speed proportions.

Using this UML Scheduling Analysis View includes all timing and scheduling parameters necessary to verify if the robotic system fulfills the timing requirements. It considers the software and the mechanical part and brings them all in one place.

The actual analysis of the timing/scheduling requirements is very complex, because of the amount of tasks, their parameters (priorities, periods, deadlines, etc.), their dependencies between each other and the possible influence of other tasks on the response times by blocking a resource. Specialized tools are necessary (e.g. SymTA/S (Henia, Hamann, Jersak, Racu, Richter & Ernst, 2005), Times (Fersman & Yi, 2004)). Additionally, the mechanical aspects have to be taken into account, too. The total requirement is to fulfill the complete process. This includes the mechanical tasks and the software calculation, i.e. the software tasks.

With this information captured in the UML Scheduling Analysis View, it is possible to use an automatic transformation to the analysis tool SymTA/S by Syntavision to verify the timing requirement without the effort of having the system remodeled in the analysis tool (Hagner & Goltz, 2010).

The transformation creates a corresponding SymTA/S model and makes it possible to analyze the system. After the successful analysis, the results are published back into the UML Scheduling analysis view. Therefore, the developer sees the result in the UML model.

Figure 8. Activity diagram of the mechanical flow.

Figure 9 depicts the scheduling analysis result of the mechanical part as a Gantt chart. The result shows, that the worst case response time (the time after which the complete task chain is finished) is 1.1 s. This result is on the borderline to fulfill the requirement of 1.0 s per cycle. Adaptronic joints can be used as additional, distributed brakes so that braking is initiated later and mean speed is higher. Additionally, adaptronic joints are used to reduce oscillations of the structure after braking, so that positioning of the gripper can start earlier. If a reduction of 10% during the move and during the positioning task can be realized (speed factor 0.9) the response time can be reduced and the requirement will be fulfilled.

The scheduling analysis of the software part is done, too. The result shows, that the system is schedulable, all deadlines are met, and the utilization of the resources is not too high.

CONCLUSION

This contribution shows an integrated modeling approach to consider requirements in an interdisciplinary development project. Targets and requirements on system level are consistently decomposed into requirements for different

Figure 9. Gantt chart of the analysis result of the mechanical part.

disciplines. Although, specific development, testing and verification techniques in the different disciplines have to be used, the consistent fulfillment of requirements is monitored and possible goal conflicts are identified as soon as in the early phases.

The first step was to find a common way to describe requirements from different knowledge domains with one modeling approach, so that relations between requirements and other system objects could be placed and the whole system could be analyzed. On the other hand the approach must allow the use of other (modeling) techniques in the different domains for later development phases. But it still must be able to bring the results together to decide about the fulfillment of requirements in the big system context. In this project SysML and UML were used to model the system and to realize a verification of the time related requirements with the same verification methods and tools.

The approach was demonstrated for parallel robots. New challenges turn up for highly flexible robotic systems. These systems consist of more components (segments, drives, control units, etc.). A sophisticated domain integrated requirements modeling, system analysis, and verification becomes more and more important. Therefore, the shown approach will be extended and investigated for these new challenges.

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